

Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health 2026

Conference Proceedings

Editor Dr. Daniel Biggs

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Academy of Sport and Wellbeing

The background of the lower half of the cover is a dark, textured surface with several bright orange slices and whole oranges scattered across it. The oranges are vibrant and appear fresh, with some showing the white pith and segments.

HIGHER EDUCATION

Celebration of
Student-led Research

CONTINUED PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Peer assisted learning

STUDENT VOICE

Students as partners

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The Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health is a celebration and recognition of UHI Perth's student work throughout the academic year 2025-2026. This event showcases poster presentations spanning from Higher National Certificates at level 7 to Fourth Year Undergraduate Degrees at level 10. The posters feature research based on Graded Units and Dissertations, highlighting the academic achievements and innovative contributions of our students in the fields of Sport, Health and Outdoor Education.

Student Conference

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Conference Proceedings Editor – Dr. Daniel Biggs

UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health
1st June 2026
Academy of Sport and Wellbeing

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The Thematic Statement of the Student Conference

The learning of research skills within sport and health sciences plays an important role in developing informed, analytical, and adaptable graduates. As both sectors increasingly rely on evidence-based practice, students must go beyond theoretical understanding and develop the ability to interpret, evaluate, and apply research in real-world settings. This supports academic development and prepares students for professional roles across sport, health, and wellbeing industries. A key benefit is the development of critical thinking and evidence-based decision-making. Practitioners in sport and health must justify their decisions using reliable and current evidence rather than opinion or tradition. For example, training, rehabilitation, and health interventions should be supported by research. Research literacy enables students to assess evidence quality and avoid outdated practice (Smith & Sparkes, 2016).

In coaching, strength and conditioning, sports therapy, or health promotion, these skills improve adaptability and effectiveness (Bishop et al., 2019). Skill-based hiring trends further highlight the importance of applied competencies such as data interpretation and problem-solving (Bone et al., 2023). Importantly, these skills are highly transferable. Data analysis, communication, critical thinking, and problem-solving are valuable across education, business, public services, and policy roles. Additionally, reflective practice also supports continuous improvement and lifelong learning, which are essential in dynamic industries (Knowles et al., 2020).

Overall, research skills in sport and health sciences provide more than academic development. They enhance employability, strengthen professional practice, and equip students with transferable skills for multiple career pathways.

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Aim

To investigate the psychological impact of sports injury on individuals, identifying key factors that influence emotional and mental health outcomes during rehabilitation and recovery.

- Objective 1:** To explore how athletic identity/loss affects individuals' emotional and mental well-being following sports injury.
- Objective 2:** To examine how injury type, severity and duration influence psychological responses during recovery.
- Objective 3:** To analyse the psychological strain experienced during rehabilitation and how it affects motivation, resilience and progression towards return-to-play outcomes.

Introduction

Sports injuries are common in athletes and can significantly influence both rehabilitation and return-to-play outcomes (Wiese-Bjornstal et al., 1998). In addition to physical limitations, injury often triggers psychological and emotional responses such as anxiety, reduced confidence and fear of re-injury, which may affect motivation and engagement with the recovery process. These responses are shaped by individual perception, injury severity and time away from sport, highlighting the complex nature of recovery. As a result, sports injuries present not only physical challenges but also important implications for mental and emotional well-being (Smith, Scott, and Wiese, 1990).

Overview

This study examines the complex relationship between psychological and physical responses to sports injury, with a focus on how emotional and cognitive factors influence rehabilitation outcomes. By exploring athletic identity, injury characteristics and psychological strain, the research highlights how these factors interact to shape motivation, adherence and overall recovery progression. The findings aim to inform a more holistic, person-centered approach to sports therapy practice, supporting both psychological well-being and effective return-to-play outcomes.

Results

The findings across the three objectives highlight that psychological responses to sports injury are multifaceted and influenced by a combination of identity, injury characteristics and rehabilitation experiences.

- Objective 1:** Athletic identity disruption was identified as a key psychological response following injury. Individuals with a strong identification with their sporting role experienced greater emotional distress, including reduced self-worth, loss of confidence and feelings of detachment from sport (Liu et al., 2025; Lochbaum et al., 2022). However, some individuals demonstrated the ability to reconstruct their identity through alternative roles such as coaching or modified participation, supporting continued engagement (Liu et al., 2025).
- Objective 2:** Injury type, severity and duration were shown to significantly influence psychological well-being. Prolonged injury and extended time away from sport were associated with increased anxiety, frustration and reduced confidence (Sheehan et al., 2024). Psychological responses were also shaped by environmental and social factors, highlighting the importance of support systems during recovery (Sheehan et al., 2024).
- Objective 3:** During rehabilitation, individuals experienced a range of psychological and emotional responses including fear of re-injury, uncertainty, isolation and fluctuating motivation (Jaekel et al., 2025). These responses were dynamic and evolved throughout different stages of recovery. Structured rehabilitation programmes, goal-setting and positive social support were identified as key factors in improving adherence and emotional well-being (Jaekel et al., 2025; Sheehan et al., 2024).

Key findings / Conclusion

This project explored the psychological impact of sports injury and identified key factors influencing emotional and mental health during recovery. The findings demonstrate that injury disrupts not only physical function but also self-concept, confidence and psychological stability. Athletic identity loss, injury characteristics and emotional strain were shown to be closely linked, collectively shaping rehabilitation progression and return-to-play readiness.

Athletes with a strong identification with sport were particularly vulnerable to emotional distress when participation was restricted. Prolonged injury duration and uncertainty surrounding recovery further intensified anxiety and reduced perceived control. Throughout rehabilitation, fluctuating emotions such as frustration, fear of re-injury and diminished confidence were found to influence motivation, engagement and adherence to rehabilitation programmes. These findings reinforce that psychological recovery is an essential component of overall rehabilitation rather than secondary to physical healing.

From a sports therapy perspective, these findings highlight the importance of adopting holistic, person-centered rehabilitation approaches. Incorporating psychological screening, structured goal setting and strategies to maintain athlete involvement within their sporting environment may improve adherence, enhance resilience and support safer, more effective return-to-play outcomes. Recognising and addressing psychological factors is therefore fundamental to optimising rehabilitation and advancing sports therapy practice.

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How Does Wearable Technology Influence Exercise Adherence Within General Population Adults?

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Purpose

Using a mixed-methods approach, this study aimed to understand how wearable technology influences exercise adherence in general population adults.

Introduction

Wearable technology is widely used to monitor physical activity, with increased adoption across the general population through various device formats. Devices provide feedback through metrics such as step count, heart rate, and activity tracking, positioning them as tools to support behaviour change. However, the impact on long-term exercise adherence remains inconsistent. Evidence shows initial increases in activity are often followed by disengagement once novelty declines (Ferguson *et al.*, 2022).

From a motivational perspective, wearable technology relies heavily on external feedback, which may limit the development of autonomous, self-determined behaviour.

This study addresses a key gap in the literature by combining quantitative data gained from questionnaire responses with qualitative insight gathered from semi structured interviews to examine how wearable technology influences exercise behaviour over time.

Results

A total of 78 participants completed the survey with 59% of participants exercising four or more times per week and only a small proportion reporting low activity levels. This indicates that the sample largely consisted of individuals already engaged in regular exercise, which is important when interpreting adherence outcomes. As wearable technology is often more effective at supporting existing behaviours rather than initiating them, this high baseline activity may explain the consistently positive adherence results observed.

Figure 1 demonstrates that wearable technology was widely perceived as a motivational tool, with 74% of participants agreeing or strongly agreeing that it improved their motivation to be physically active. Negative responses were minimal, indicating generally favourable perceptions. This supports the role of wearable devices in enhancing short-term motivation through feedback, goal setting, and self-monitoring. However, as this reflects perceived motivation rather than sustained behaviour, it should not be interpreted as evidence of long-term adherence.

Figure 2 highlights more varied responses in relation to psychological impact. While most participants did not report feeling pressured or dependent on wearable devices, a notable minority experienced feelings of guilt, stress, or increased reliance on feedback. This suggests that wearable technology does not produce uniform psychological responses and may introduce unintended pressure for some users. These findings reinforce the idea that while wearables can support behaviour, their impact is dependent on individual interpretation and context.

Psychological & Behavioural Impact of Wearables

- Findings indicate that wearable technology functions as a facilitator rather than a driver of exercise behaviour. Quantitative results showed consistently high adherence across all groups, suggesting behaviour was already established. This was supported by interview data, where participants described wearable devices as reinforcing existing routines through feedback and self-monitoring rather than creating new habits. This aligns with Patel *et al.* (2015), who argue that wearable devices support behaviour change but rarely initiate or sustain it independently.

- Interviews provided insight into the mechanisms underpinning this pattern. Participants highlighted how progress tracking and goal-based feedback supported motivation and accountability, but these effects were dependent on continuous feedback and visible progression. Where progress plateaued, motivation declined, indicating reliance on external reinforcement.

- A key theme from the interviews was the emergence of psychological pressure and data dependence, with some participants describing behaviour being driven by targets, streaks, and notifications. This suggests a shift towards externally regulated motivation, which may limit long-term adherence.

- Overall, wearable technology is most effective when supporting already active individuals. Its impact is conditional on user motivation and context, rather than inherent to the technology itself.

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The focus of this study was to effectively research, compare and analyse the effects and benefits in the treatment of shoulder impingement injuries, comparing soft tissue therapy and steroid injections. using current research.

Aims

The study aimed to investigate the effects and benefits of soft tissue therapy compared with steroid injections, in the treatment of shoulder impingements. Aiming to establish the advantages, and disadvantages of both treatment methods while researching the effectiveness of the treatment in the long term.

One objective was researching whether a combination of the modalities was more advantageous in aiding recovery. The modalities that were researched were soft tissue therapies such as mobilisation, manual therapy, specific targeted exercises plus surgery as a treatment method, some of these were looked at individually and some were treated in a combination, for example mobilisation combined with targeted assisted exercises. The research used was the most current and was secondary research, due to already being published and a reliable and credible source of research for the study.

Results

Table 1. Prevalence of shoulder injuries across sports.

Injury/Sport	Basketball		Handball		Swimming		Tennis		Volleyball		Water-polo		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
All athletes	61		25		30		28		56		37		237	
Male	39	64	12	48	16	53	10	36	31	55	37	100	152	64
Female	22	36	13	52	14	47	18	64	25	45	-	-	85	36
Athletes with shoulder injuries	8	62	6	75	7	78	2	40	6	38	14	100	43	66
Male	5	38	2	25	2	22	3	60	10	62	-	-	22	34
Female	3	23.1	3	38.0	4	44.4	2	40.0	5	31.0	6	43.0	23	
Male	2		2		2		1		2		6		15	
Female	1		1		2		1		3		-		8	

Shoulder impingements are the third most common injury within the sporting industry, specifically in overhead sports such as volleyball, tennis and swimming, with 44% of injuries being shoulder impingement.

References

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Tauqeer, S., Arooj, A. and Shakeel, H. (2024). Effects of manual therapy in addition to stretching and strengthening exercises to improve scapular range of motion, functional capacity and pain in patients with shoulder impingement syndrome: a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, (online)

Results

It has been shown that steroid injections have an effective place within treatment as a short-term modality, reducing pain levels significantly while allowing for consistency in movement during the recovery period/rehabilitation.

Whilst reviewing different treatment options (supervised exercise, at home exercises, manual therapy, surgery, motion with mobilisation, physiotherapy, advice only from physician and combined surgery and exercise) the studies analysed indicated that exercise alongside manual/physical therapy, showed the most positive results within the treatments overall.

The data gathered suggests within long term recovery treatment, regular exercise improved pain levels and range of motion as much as the surgery following the combination of surgery followed by the exercise plan.

FIGURE 2. Glenohumeral posterior glide mobilization.

FIGURE 2. Glenohumeral posterior glide mobilization.

The Impact of COVID-19 on Sports Engagement and Coaches

Shane McCrosson

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Introduction

This project examines how COVID-19 has influenced sports engagement and coaches in Scotland, highlighting a key challenge for the sector. It explores some of the effects of the pandemic and barriers to renewed participation among participants and coaches.

Understanding these effects is vital for monitoring recovery and developing strategies to enhance involvement and support coaches' resilience. The findings presented are informed by primary research, as well as library and online investigations.

Project Aim

To evaluate how COVID-19 affected sports participation across different demographics in Scotland and to understand how the pandemic influenced coaching practices, opportunities, and career development.

Objectives

- 1) Through academic research, identify changes in sports participation before and during COVID-19 across age groups and communities, as well as impacts experienced by coaches.
- 2) Collect and analyse questionnaire data from individual participating in sports pre-pandemic and compare it with academic findings.
- 3) Evaluate how COVID-19 affected coaches' mental health, workload, and professional development through surveys and interviews.

Methodology

Secondary Research:

- ❖ **Library and Web-based:** Government surveys, academic papers, and international studies.

Primary Research:

- ❖ **Questionnaires:** Separate surveys for participants and coaches using JISC; distributed online, through social media, personal contacts and via QR codes.
- ❖ **Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews with coaches, conducted via phone, Zoom, or in person; recorded and transcribed.

	Adults participating in physical activity/sport (including walking)			Percentage of adults engaging in recreational walking			Adults participating in physical activity/sport (excluding walking)		
	Men	Women	All	Men	Women	All	Men	Women	All
2019	82%	78%	80%	67%	69%	68%	58%	50%	54%
2020	87%	85%	86%	82%	82%	82%	48%	41%	44%
2021	87%	84%	85%	78%	80%	79%	60%	53%	56%
2022	84%	80%	82%	73%	75%	74%	57%	46%	51%

Age	Male			Female			Total
	EA	FA	OA	EA	FA	OA	
18-25	28	1	2	12	4	0	40
26-35	1	2	-	3	4	-	7
36-50	2	3	-	3	5	-	8
51-65	3	3	-	3	6	-	9
66+	0	1	-	1	1	-	2
Total	36	10	0	20	56	0	76

Age	Levels of Activity Before Covid19 (Male)			Levels of Activity After Covid19 (Female)		
	EA	FA	OA	EA	FA	OA
18-25	8	13	5	2	-	-
26-35	-	1	2	-	1	-
36-50	-	2	-	-	1	-
51-65	-	1	2	-	1	2
66+	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	8	14	8	2	3	2

Age	Levels of Activity Before Covid19 (Male)			Levels of Activity After Covid19 (Female)		
	EA	FA	OA	EA	FA	OA
18-25	4	11	8	3	2	4
26-35	2	-	1	-	1	-
36-50	-	1	-	-	2	1
51-65	-	2	1	-	1	1
66+	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	6	13	11	3	2	5

Age	Impact on Physical Health (Male)			Impact on Mental Health (Male)				
	A/Lot	Reasonable	Slightly	None	A/Lot	Reasonable	Slightly	None
18-25	6	6	11	5	4	6	8	10
26-35	1	-	-	2	1	1	1	1
36-50	-	-	2	-	-	1	1	-
51-65	-	-	2	1	-	-	1	2
66+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	7	6	15	8	5	8	10	13

Age	Impact on Physical Health (Female)			Impact on Mental Health (Female)				
	A/Lot	Reasonable	Slightly	None	A/Lot	Reasonable	Slightly	None
18-25	1	5	3	3	3	3	6	-
26-35	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
36-50	-	1	2	-	-	3	-	-
51-65	-	1	1	1	-	2	1	-
66+	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	2	8	6	4	3	6	4	1

Discussion

Objective 1 – Participation Trends

- ❖ Research identified modest increases in adult activity (2012–2017); men more active than women.
- ❖ Government surveys showed activity declined significantly with age, and alarming drops among young people, especially adolescent girls.
- ❖ COVID-19 caused a sharp fall in participation, especially among the youngest and oldest.
- ❖ Many coaches stopped coaching, though some moved online.

Objective 2 – Questionnaire Findings

- ❖ Slight drop in men's activity; larger drop for women.
- ❖ 66% want to be more active; main barriers are lack of time and opportunities.
- ❖ Younger people and men generally remained more active.
- ❖ COVID-19 notably affected physical and mental health, especially for younger participants.

Objective 3 – Coaching Impacts

- ❖ **Key Themes:** Loss of income, disruption to coaching and volunteering, increased time for reflection, opportunities for upskilling and social isolation.
- ❖ **Changes:** Remote coaching, descriptive methods, and adaptations to restrictions with some changes remaining permanent, e.g. greater participant autonomy and club closures.
- ❖ **Other Impacts:** Reduced participant numbers and shorter attention spans after lockdown.
- ❖ **Findings:** Echoed global concerns about income, isolation, digital skill gaps, and align with UK Coaching's observations regarding upskilling.
- ❖ **Quantitative Survey Results:** reinforced the loss of opportunities and job uncertainty.

Conclusion

COVID-19 reduced activity levels for both men and women, with women's fitness most affected. Walking for recreation increased during the pandemic. Younger people experienced greater mental-health impacts, while older adults were more resilient. A major long-term issue is the loss of volunteers and coaches, with organisations struggling to rebuild. Coaches faced insecurity but some adapted through online delivery. Continued efforts are needed to rebuild participation, support coaches, and remove barriers to sport.

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Does aerobic exercise improve motor function in individuals with Parkinson's Disease

Introduction

Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative condition characterised by motor impairment, including tremor, rigidity and postural instability: symptoms often lead to reduced mobility, balance deficits and decreased quality of life (Andreas Wolfgang Wolff et al 2023). Aerobic exercise including treadmill training, cycling, have shown to be a great intervention due to improved cardiovascular fitness, motor performance and neuroplasticity.

Literature Review

Aerobic exercise has been shown to significantly improve motor symptoms in individuals with Parkinson's disease, with reduction observed in Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS III) scores following intervention (Choi et al., 2020). Choi is a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials (RTC), comparing 18 RTC with > 1000 participants, demonstrating consistent improvements in motor function following exercise intervention. Showing that aerobic exercise produces clinically meaningful improvements in motor control rather than simply maintaining function. Studies have also shown to improve gait speed, stride length and functional mobility (Timed up and go) following aerobic training intervention (Radder et al 2020). Following aerobic intervention, it translates into functional improvements that are directly relevant to daily activities and independence. Moderate to high-intensity aerobic exercise has been associated with greater improvements in motor function compared to low-intensity training (Schnekmann et al 2018). Highlighting the importance of appropriate exercise prescription, suggesting that higher intensity training may optimise rehabilitation outcomes. Aerobic exercise intervention have also shown to improve the quality-of-life measures in individuals with Parkinson's (Chen et al 2020). Suggesting that benefits extend beyond motor function, positively impacting overall wellbeing and participation.

Results

Effect of Aerobic Exercise on Motor Function in Parkinson's Disease

Comparison of Gait Speed: PD vs Post-Exercise vs Healthy Norms

Discussion

The findings from this review suggest that moderate to high aerobic exercise produces clinically meaningful improvements in motor function in individuals with PD. Consistent reduction in UPDRS III scores, alongside improvement in gait speed and functional mobility, showcases that aerobic interventions are effective in addressing key motor impairments associated with PD.

Evidence indicated that exercise intensity and duration are a significant factors in influencing outcomes, with moderate (60-65% max heart rate) to high intensity (80-85% max heart rate) programme delivered over longer periods (>12 weeks) showing to have greater benefits (Schnekmann et al 2018). These findings support the concept that aerobic exercises is not only beneficial but has an appropriate prescription that has optimise outcomes.

Literature does highlight several limitations, including variability in intervention design, small sample sizes and limited-long-term follow up. It would be suggested that having further research is required to establish a standardised guideline for exercise prescription, including optimal intensity, frequency and duration.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In a clinical setting, the findings support the integration of aerobic exercise into routine management of clients with PD. There needs to be a structured programme such as treadmill training / cycling to be considered, with progression tailored to the individual's functional capacity. Additionally, group-based or supervised interventions may enhance adherence and long-term engagement.

Aerobic exercises is an effective and essential component of PD management. However, its success depends on targeted, progressive and appropriately prescribed rehabilitation programs. Therefore, clinicians play a critical role in prescribing and monitoring exercise intensity to maximise neuroplastic adaptation, reduce functional decline and improve long term independence in individuals with PD.

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Background

Menopause: the date in time when a woman has not menstruated for 12 calendar months (NICE, 2019)

More women are running, but the gender research gap remains (Andersen, 2019; Cowley et al, 2021)

Current training guidance is largely based on **male cohorts** (Rothschild, 2024)

Menopause: falling oestrogen levels are associated with **accelerated musculoskeletal changes and reduced recovery capacity** (Rothschild, 2024)

Aim

To examine the prevalence and rate of injuries sustained in menopausal female distance runners.

Methods

Online questionnaire (n=227), Peri- and postmenopausal runners

Data: 40 questions examining training habits, injury history, wellbeing, HRT use

Over 80% of runners reported at least 1 injury during the menopausal transition

Results

- **80% reported injury** during menopausal transition & 23% reported injury during the previous 4 weeks
- **Strength training associated with injury** ($p < 0.005$) likely reflecting a reactive rather than causative relationship
- **Higher weekly mileage and more years of running experience** trend towards higher injury prevalence (ns)
- This suggests a potential link between **injury rate and declining oestrogen levels**
- Runners report a **focus on behaviour change and recovery strategies**

References

Andersen, (2019), 'The State of Running 2019', <https://runrepeat.com/state-of-running>
Cowley et al, (2021), "Invisible Sportswomen" The sex data gap in sport and exercise science research', *Women in Sport and Physical Activity Journal*

Negative Impact of Menopause on Wellbeing (n = 227)

■ % of respondents expressing negative impact on QOL measures

QUALITATIVE FINDINGS:

'I just lurch from one injury to another'

"More protein, more recovery, more sleep"

'Symptoms have eased & I'm beginning to feel healthier than before'

Presentation References (Harvard)

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